

Effect of Mother Tongue on Performance in Concept Erosion among Primary School Students in Faskari Educational Zone, Katsina-State

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Abstract

This study x-rays the effect of Mother tongue on performance in concept erosion among primary school students in Faskari Educational Zone, Katsina-State. The study adopted quasi experimental research design (pre-test, treatment, post-test). The population of the study consists of all primary five students in Faskari local government education authority. Intact classes in two primary schools were randomly selected as samples. The objective of the study aimed to examine the mean performance score of students exposed to concept erosion using Mother tongue medium of instruction and those taught using English languages in Faskari Educational Zone, Katsina state. The research question and hypothesis are in line with the objective of the study. Mother Tongue Performance Test (MTPT) containing thirty multiple choice items was used as the research instrument. The instrument yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.83. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research question while, t-test was used in testing the hypothesis. The finding of the study revealed that, students taught concept erosion using Mother tongue medium of instruction performed academically better than those taught using English language. Based on the finding, the study recommended that, Mother tongue should be made the language of instruction at the primary school level and eventually at all levels of education in Katsina state.

Keywords: Mother Tongue, Academic Performance, Erosion and Students

Introduction

Primary school education is the first stage of formal education. It is considered as the bedrock to further learning in achieving basic literacy, numeracy as well as establishing solid foundations in science and other related subjects and disciplines. Kabir (2016) maintained that primary school is a place where teaching and learning are practicalized, knowledge and skills are acquired and advanced, attitudes and values are internalized and educational ends are met. This is why any meaningful learning and subsequent educational fortunes and achievements are tied to a successful primary education.

In the act of learning, learners obtain content knowledge, values, positive attitudes, skills and develop work habit and practice the application of all upper mentioned to real life situation; application that has bearing on performance. Performance represents a set of strategies for the acquisition and application of knowledge and skills through tasks that are meaningful and engaging to learners. Teachers can therefore determine the extent to which learners acquire relevant curriculum content by assessing their performance. In the recognition of the importance and contributions of language to education (especially at the primary school level) that the Federal Ministry of Education in collaboration with other statutory agencies included in the National Policy of Education 2013 as reported by Okudo (2013) stipulated that instructions in primary schools should be solely in the Mother tongue or the language of the immediate community. Subsequently, English language can be used as the language of instruction at secondary school level and at higher institutions. It is this policy of adopting Mother tongue as a medium of instruction at primary schools and the subsequent shift to English language as a medium of instruction at the post primary education that formed the basis of this study.

There are arguments and counter arguments for and against the language policy in question: “that instruction at the primary school should be given in Mother tongue after which at the post primary education, instruction should be switched to English Language”. This issue is becoming more problematic in the sense that a number of scholars are contradicting each other as to which approach / medium is appropriate for instruction at the primary school level which all considered to be a central stage of formal education. Advocates for the adoption of Mother tongue as the medium of instruction such as (Ogunbiyi, 2008; Olagbaju, 2009 in Adeleye & Ogunremi, 2017) are of the view that proper development of a child is closely related to the frequent use of the language he/she is used to. In essence, through exercising Mother tongue as the medium of instruction, the child acquired at the very early stage, self-confidence, initiatives, resourcefulness, creative reasoning and adaptability, that is, skills necessary for further growth in the later stage of educational development. Hence, by adopting Mother tongue medium of instruction, the individual child is groomed to laying the foundation of further developments which he/she likely is in a position to build upon in later years in another language.

Furthermore, Elumelu (2017) and Ogbonna (2017); strongly opined that education should be given through the medium of Mother tongue in the formative years (1-12) and that, this should extend to as late a stage as possible. To them providing education through Mother tongue will offer the child an opportunity to explore the natural environment, develop curiosity, reasoning ability and engender self-confidence. They maintained that the use of Mother tongue in the teaching-learning process in the early years (at primary school level) helps not only in preserving one’s culture and values, but also develop it lexically. Fernando (2020) maintained that, Mother tongue is the language a child has acquired first experiences of life, dreams, thinks and confidently and conveniently expresses feelings and emotions. To ignore the child familiar language as soon as he/she comes to school is like taking the child away from home.

In addition, Mother tongue is an indispensable instrument for the development of the intellectual, moral and physical aspects of education. It is a subject of thought and by which other thoughts can be tackled, understood and communicated. Clarity of thought and expression is only possible when one has a certain command over the mother tongue. Weakness in any other subject means weakness in that subject only; weakness in the mother tongue means the paralysis of all thought and the power of expression, deep insight, fresh discoveries, appreciation and expansion of ideas. In line with this notion, Adebayor (2002) in Isyaku (2017) defined Mother tongue as the language which a group of people considered to be inhabitants of an area acquire in the early years and which eventually becomes their natural instrument of thought and communication. Moreover, Mother tongue can be defined in a number of ways that depicts the following variables such as; by origin, which is the language one has first spoken at the early childhood or the language which one has established the first long lasting verbal contact. Through internal identification, which is the language one identifies with as a speaker of by the people around him for his/her ability to manipulate the language to suit his claim and thoughts. Others are: external identification which implies the language one is identified with as a speaker by others who consider his/her dialect and accent as unique to a particular community. Competence which signifies the language one knows and can manipulate best; and by function, which is the language one uses most and exercises a lot of command in deliberations and activities.

In whatever view point, Mother tongue is the first language that a person learned. In this regard and in the teaching-learning process, Mother tongue of a child is of utmost importance. It categorizes a large part of the child’s environment that has names for all the objects. Considering the relevance of Mother tongue in the teaching-learning process, Kabir, (2016) has disclosed the following advantages of Mother tongue in the instructional process, thus: Mother tongue medium of instruction promotes the psycho-emotional wellbeing of the learner as it ensures a smooth transition from home to school. It deepens the orientation of the child’s socio-cultural environment. It enhances patriotism in order to empower and strengthen good citizens, integrate the child soundly into the creative cultural-environment and ensure the unique survival of the child. It facilitates learning by maintaining high motivation level. Hence, any sudden break from the Mother tongue to which the learner is both psychologically and socio-culturally attached may introduce feelings of inadequacy and resentment towards self, teacher and school. It leads to continuity in cognitive maturations. In this situation, schools should build on already acquired experiences at home instead of breaking or frustrating the intellectual process. Linguistic research has shown that, at the age of five, the child has acquired some fluency and competency in an appropriate and developmental task which the school should continue to promote and to ensure the child’s early activation of potentials. Mother tongue helps in the quicker acquisition, retention and dissemination and use of knowledge in other subject areas.

Mother tongue instruction encourages children to learn the basic rudiments of modern science and technology in their own language. Obanya (2004) in Oyekola (2020) asserts that Mother tongue instruction, if properly handled, can contribute to our overall national development. Hence, as long as science and technology are transmitted in Mother tongue, so long the scientific and technological development is transmitted in children and youth which will open the door of opportunity for

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technological advancement of Nigeria as a Nation. In this respect and of a reasonable perspective, a Nigerian child should be encouraged from the start to develop curiosity, initiatives, manipulative abilities, spontaneous flexibility and manual dexterity. He/she should acquire these skills and attitudes through Mother tongue. This is where the average European or English child has an added advantage over his Nigerian counterpart. While the former is acquiring new skills at primary education in his mother tongue, the latter is busy struggling with a foreign language during the greater part of his primary education. Critics have argued that, early instruction in one's Mother tongue could have negative effect on the learner. They further stressed that, transition from Mother tongue to the English which is the official language in Nigeria will be difficult and that, the official language will never be sufficiently mastered to enable the learner fit properly in to the national elite life (Olaofe, 2010 & Aliyu, 2019). They further argued that, intellectual development will be hindered by the need to cope with the demands of two languages (the mother tongue and the official language, English).

On the other hand, English language as one of the most prominent and prestigious language in the world is adopted as the official language in Nigeria. As a multilingual nation, Nigeria uses English as a unifying language among people. It enhances socialization and promotes mutual intelligibility among different ethnic groups. It is the language of instruction in all the higher institutions of learning. Most school texts are printed in English. It is a subject in itself and a specialized discipline in its own context. Admission in to higher institutions, especially, the university is based on the competency in English. Amodu (2012) asserts that, English language has become integral if not indispensable to our national history. It is not just a first or second language to many Nigerians, but also an official language of the entire country with all its educational, technological, legislative, and diplomatic functions.

Supporters of adopting English language as the medium of instruction at the primary and all schools level like (Amodu, 2012 & Aliyu, 2019) are of the view that, early exposure of children to English language will help prepare them to achieve mastery and fluency. They believed that, children at the age of seven and below, stands the chance of achieving the inter language and fluency as the natives can do. This is so because, the language acquisition device (LAD) only freezes at the age of twelve. Amodu (2012) have strongly asserted that, English language has an increasing recognition in helping the learners cope effectively with the challenges of learning, development of skills, educational transformation as well as instructional effectiveness. Education system is in dire need of positive transformation, most especially in the teaching-learning process at the primary school level. Hence, English language will serve as the bedrock of success in other fields of study as comprehending those fields of endeavor depends largely on its effective usage.

Critics further argued that most indigenous languages (Mother tongue) are too under developed and not sophisticated enough to take cognizance of scientific terms and technical thoughts. They entertain fears that most Mother tongues in Nigeria has no technical development of language that is, writing form, body of creative writing, vocabulary and register appropriate to a variety of specialized technical areas and discourse modes. Less than 10% of all indigenous languages in Nigeria were transformed into writing form (Ohia, 2001, in Odusesu, 2016). In addition, it is a well-known fact that an over whelming majority of indigenous language in Nigeria do not meet the standardized criteria required of a language in such situation, thus; How do you explain mathematical equations and conduct scientific experiment?

Advocates of the mother tongue instruction believed that these arguments are not supported by available research evidence and experiences but rather fear of the unknown. What arguments of this nature tend to ignore is that living languages do grow by adapting to the demands of the changing times. Thus, as soon as a language encounters new experiences or phenomenon, it progressively finds an appropriate term for it. To develop Mother tongue scientifically and technologically, translation of key terminologies is all that is required. In this context, translation is an operation performed on a language that involves a process of substituting a text in one language for a text in another. Oluwole (2008) draws attention to the fact that for languages with fairly stable or settled orthographies, as in the case of Hausa and Yoruba, creating indigenous technical terms is all that is required. For example, in Hausa language, "Yanan Gizo" for internet, "Na'ura mai kwakwalwa" for computer and so on. Ogbonna (2017) further states that, the great and developed nations of the world, the individualized high-performance nations are those that have acquired skills based on their native languages. Hence, Nigeria should not be excluded.

It is pertinent to stress the relevance of Basic Science as a core subject at primary school level. One of the developments that deserve commendation associated with the National Policy of Education is the pride of place it has accorded Basic Science as a compulsory subject which all primary school pupils cannot dispense with in their learning activities. It is believed that, teaching and learning Basic Science could establish a strong avenue for the production of science based pupils that will further promote scientific and technological advancements needed for development of the nation. Hence, it is in the recognition of the need for inculcating into young pupils the right type of skills and integrated disciplinary orientation in the study of science, that call for its inclusion in the primary school curriculum.

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Basic science is a body of organized knowledge and a process of inquiry which deals with the basic ideas, methods and objectives in finding out about things in our environment. Sharehu (2010) identified the components which ought to be reflected in instructional process on Basic science such as information which includes facts, formulas, principles and explanations. Process through which scientist think and work, design experiments to answer questions, solve problems and gain information. Creativity; which means visualizing scientific principles, imaging solutions to puzzles and connecting ideas. Attitudinal which includes: self-image and personal confidence in personal scientific ability and societal role. Personal relevance which involves: applications and connections to the environment. Moreover, when Basic science is taught to reflect all these domains, pupils acquire scientific skills, like observation, measurement, classification, and attitudes like, open-mindedness, honesty, perseverance and curiosity among others. Based on the foregoing perspectives, it is endorsed that in any attempt that is geared at improving pupils' academic performance, the relevant instructional medium can never be over emphasized. Medium of instruction is highly considered as the process of classroom interaction which contributes to the effectiveness or otherwise of any teaching learning process (Ogbonna, 2017).

Basic Science in primary school is believed to be the foundation of creating scientific minds in pupils (Sharehu, 2010). Despite the relevance attached to the subject in the curriculum as the prerequisite to study science related courses at the secondary and tertiary institution levels, available data obtained from Faskari Local Government Education Authority revealed an alarming rate of failure of 68% of primary school pupils in Basic Science in 2021/2022 Science and Technical schools entrance examination.

Table 1: 2021/2022 Entrance Examination Result in Basic Science

Gender	No. of Candidates	No. of Pass	No. of Fail	% Pass	% Fail
Male	374	107	267	21	53
Female	127	53	74	11	15
Total:	501	160	341	32	68

(Faskari Local Government Education Authority, 2022).

Different scholars (Dahiru, 2016; Isyaku, 2017 & Salisu, 2017) have revealed positive perspectives on the effectiveness of the mother tongue medium of instruction in the teaching learning process at the primary school level. In spite of this, therefore, this study intends to examine effect of mother tongue on performance in concept erosion among primary school students in Faskari Educational Zone, Katsina state.

Objective of the Study

The objective of the study was to:

Examine the mean performance score of students exposed to concept erosion using Mother tongue medium of instruction and those taught using English language in Faskari Educational Zone, Katsina-State.

Research Question

The following question was raised for the study:

What is the difference between mean performance score of students exposed to concept erosion using Mother tongue medium of instruction and those taught using English language in Faskari Educational Zone, Katsina-State?

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was formulated based on the research question:

There is no significant difference between mean performance score of students exposed to concept erosion using Mother tongue medium of instruction and those taught using English language in Faskari Educational Zone, Katsina-State.

Methodology

This study focuses on the effect of Mother tongue on performance in concept erosion among primary school students in Faskari Educational Zone, Katsina-State. The study adopted quasi experimental research design (pre-test, treatment, post-test). The study aimed to examine the mean performance score of students exposed to concept erosion using Mother tongue medium of instruction and those taught using English language in Faskari Educational Zone, Katsina state. The research question and hypothesis are in line with the objective of the study. The population of the study consists of all primary five students in Faskari local government education authority. To this effect, seven thousand two hundred and thirty-three (7,233) primary five pupils of 2022/2023 academic session consisting of (4,567) male and (2,666) female was the population of the study. Intact classes in two primary schools were randomly selected as samples. Mother Tongue Performance Test (MTPT)

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was used for the study. The instrument contains thirty multiple choice items. Using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC), the instrument yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.83. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research question while, independent samples t-test was used in testing the hypothesis at 0.05 significance level using SPSS 23.0 version.

Results

Research Question

What is the difference between mean performance score of students exposed to concept erosion using Mother tongue medium of instruction and those taught using English language in Faskari Educational Zone, Katsina-State?

Table 2: Mean performance score of experimental and control groups

Group	N	\bar{X}	SD	Mean Gain.
Experimental	40	24.212	4.103	16.701
Control	40	7.511	3.645	

Table 2 revealed that there is a statistical difference in the mean score and standard deviation between the experimental and control groups in concept of erosion. The experimental group has mean score of 24.212 and the standard deviation of 4.103 while the control group has mean score of 7.511 and the standard deviation of 3.645. A mean gain of 16.701 was calculated in favor of the experimental group. This finding implies that students taught erosion using Mother tongue medium of instruction performed academically better than those taught using English language.

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between mean performance score of students exposed to concept erosion using Mother tongue medium of instruction and those taught using English language in Faskari Educational Zone, Katsina-State.

Table 3: t-test analysis of mean performance score of experimental and control groups

Group	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	p-value
Experimental	40	24.212	4.103	78	6.39	2.78	0.000
Control	40	7.511	3.645				

The t-test analysis of mean performance score of experimental and control groups taught concept erosion using Mother tongue medium of instruction and English language. The table revealed that P-value= 0.000 is less than the alpha 0.05. The t-calculated 6.39 is greater than the t-critical 2.78 at degree of freedom of 78. The hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between mean performance score of students exposed to concept erosion using Mother tongue medium of instruction and those taught using English language in Faskari Educational Zone, Katsina-State is rejected. This means that there is significant difference between mean performance score of students exposed to concept erosion using Mother tongue medium of instruction and those taught using English language in Faskari Educational Zone, Katsina-State.

Discussion of Finding

The findings of the study revealed that there is significant difference between mean performance score of students exposed to concept erosion using Mother tongue medium of instruction and those taught using English language in Faskari Educational Zone, Katsina-State. Students taught concept erosion using Mother tongue medium of instruction performed academically better than those taught using English language. This finding agrees with the findings of Elumelu, (2017); Isyaku, (2017) and Fernando, (2020) all of whom revealed that instructions in Mother tongue enhance academic performance. Adeleye and Ogunremi (2017) maintained that scientific and technological development is best expressed in the language which the child is so comfortable to twist, blend, manipulate or even break to suit his/her creative intention and capabilities. Hence, the language which can easily be twisted to suit learners needs and scientific development is the mother tongue. This study agrees with the findings of Elugbe (2000) and Oyekola (2020) that instruction in Mother tongue encourages children to learn the basic rudiments of modern science and technology in their own language. The finding of this study also supported and justified

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Oluwole (2008) that pupils become active in the teaching-learning process using Mother tongue and become passive in the process that uses English language.

Conclusion

This study has revealed that Mother tongue medium is more effective than the English language medium in teaching concept erosion in Basic Science. The study therefore concluded that Mother tongue medium of instruction is more effective in enhancing primary school pupils' academic performance in Basic Science than the English language medium.

Recommendations

Based on the finding and the conclusion drawn, the following recommendations were made:

That Mother tongue should be made the language of instruction at primary school level and subsequently at the basic and tertiary education levels. This could be made possible through the following:

1. Strengthening and advancing the National Policy of Education on Mother tongue and the language of instruction to cover all levels of education.
2. Constituting a committee of curriculum experts, subject specialists and all other stakeholders in education to come up with an integrated Mother tongue curriculum design for at least the three major Languages in the country. For the initial stage to cover all core subjects rendered in our institutions of learning and eventually, all subjects and courses.

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